

Groundwater balance modeling for optimum yield estimation in Indian atolls

Pallavi Banerjee Chattopadhyay^{1*}, Debadatta Chatterjee², Satwik Bhattacharya³ and V. S. Singh⁴

¹Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Roorkee-247667, UK, India

²Department of Geography, Jadavpur University, Kolkata – 700032, WB, India

³ Department of Geography, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221005, UP, India

⁴CSIR-National Geophysical Research Institute, Hyderabad, 500007, Telangana, India

*Corresponding author: cpallavi@es.iitr.ac.in

Abstract

The Lakshadweep Archipelago which is located southwest of India consists of numerous small coral atolls scattered across the Arabian Sea. Islanders rely solely on groundwater as their primary source of fresh water. Despite the increasing significance of groundwater in sustaining atolls, there is a regrettable dearth of systematic information necessary for optimizing aquifer yield. This research fills the gap by estimating evapotranspiration, estimating groundwater withdrawal, subsurface groundwater discharge (SGD), and recharging through rainfall. In doing so, it delineates the groundwater budget for Androth Island, a representative atoll within the Lakshadweep archipelago. The hydrodynamic study was conducted employing a groundwater balance approach that comprehensively considers the hydrological balance and the interrelationships among critical hydrodynamic parameters. These parameters include recharge from rainfall, evapotranspiration, subsurface groundwater discharge (SGD), and groundwater abstraction by local communities. The atoll receives, on an average, 1600 mm of rain per year and the amount of precipitation likely to infiltrate to recharge the aquifers is about $3 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3\text{yr}^{-1}$. The Thornthwaite method is used for estimating potential evapotranspiration (PET) at a monthly time scale, and the method incorporates day length as a factor influencing PET therefore, it emerges as the most effective means of estimating evapotranspiration in tropical atolls. The results demonstrate that an average optimum yield of $2.7 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3\text{yr}^{-1}$ and $23.06 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3\text{yr}^{-1}$ in dry and wet seasons can maintain the aquifer's current water level contours and quality. Groundwater abstraction above this limit can result in high vertical recharge from the subsurface saline zone. Overdraft may lead to shrinkage in the freshwater lens geometry, accompanied by inward movement of the transition zone. Simulation of the conceptual model illustrates how seawater intrusion can contaminate the atoll aquifer, resulting in variability in aquifer yield. The present findings reveal that while the aquifer experiences shrinkage during the dry season due to seawater intrusion, it recovers during the wet season due to seasonal recharge. Therefore, groundwater management measures may be worked out regionally to improve water quality through controlled groundwater abstraction, artificial recharge, and rainwater harvesting.

Keywords: Water sustainability, Safe yield, Groundwater balance, Atoll aquifer, Water management, Lakshadweep archipelago (India)

INTRODUCTION

Resource scarcity and environmental changes are predominantly linked to the existence of small coral island aquifers in the tropical region (Milly et al, 2005; Doll, 2009). It is reported that the low-lying atoll islands in the Indian Ocean region, face the threat of sea level rise, which are particularly susceptible to inundation and erosion. The vulnerability of these low-elevation atoll islands to the phenomenon of rising sea levels is due to global climate change and the associated melting of polar ice caps and glaciers (Shenoi et al., 1999; Masson et al., 2005). Vulnerable groundwater resources are the sole source of fresh water in the archipelago, however, intensive groundwater abstraction, driven by population growth, can lead to a rapid decline in groundwater levels (Antony et al., 2020). Urbanization and tourist development exacerbate pressures on already limited water resources, underscoring the importance of preserving both the quantity and quality of this vital resource.

The Lakshadweep coral islands constitute the world's most spectacular tropical island ecosystem, characterized by an extraordinary range of geomorphological features and climatic diversity (Goswami, 1973; Harvell et al., 1999). Aquifers are the only convenient source of freshwater in the

coral islands because of their small catchment size and high transmissivity (Morris et al., 2003). The study aims to develop a clear vision of the hydrological structure of atolls and establish a management plan that would maintain the ecosystem. Although progress has been made in defining sustainable development goals, how to achieve these changes is still debated. The challenge lies in transforming the principles of sustainable development into practicable policies that may vary across different contexts. Hydrological studies focused on small atoll aquifers have been conducted to a limited extent thus far.

The World Commission on Environment and Development (1987) defined sustainable development of environmental resources as 'development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs'. It suggests that while progress has been achieved in water resources development, policies must be upheld to ensure sustainable development for future generations. Therefore, the study aims to highlight the path toward achieving a sustainable water planning policy based on the groundwater balance approach (Sakiyan and Yazicigil, 2004; Llamas et al., 2006). The concept of safe yield is explained by many researchers (Lee, 1915; Meinzer, 1923; Todd, 1959; Bredehoeft, 1997; Sophocleous, 1997; Sophocleous and Sawin, 1997;

Dottridge and Zaber, 1999; Sophocleous, 2000; Gau and Liu, 2002; Health and Sprivill, 2003). Alley et al. (1999), Custodio, (2002), Morris et al. (2003), Alley and Leake (2004) and Maimone (2004) defined safe yield as the level of development of groundwater that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of future generations.

Many different approaches exist for estimating the safe yield of an aquifer. This paper introduces a suitable method for comprehensively estimating the water resources of an atoll by applying the water balance technique to calculate the safe yield; by comparing the total inflows to the total outflows over a specified period, the water balance of the aquifer can be determined. If the inflows exceed the outflows, the aquifer is considered to have a surplus, indicating that there is a room for additional withdrawals without depleting the aquifer. The maximum amount of water that can be withdrawn from the aquifer without causing long-term depletion or adverse impacts on water quality was considered a safe yield for the aquifer (Koumantakis et al., 1999). The concept of the water balance method states that, for any arbitrary volume and during any time, the difference between total input and output will be balanced by the change of water storage within the system. Therefore, the use of a water-balance method implies measurements of all the balance elements using independent methods.

This paper focuses on assessing the water balance and estimating the safe yield of an atoll aquifer of the Lakshadweep archipelago that is immensely populated, urbanized, and tourism-driven. Despite the sensitivity of the

island aquifer, the water cycle of the atolls is simple, as shown in Figure 1. The advantages of the simple model include accuracy, but it highly depends on data quality (Healy and Cook, 2002). Groundwater recharge through precipitation is a key component of inflow into the model. However, the measurement of groundwater recharge (GR) has long been recognized as a difficult task. Accurate estimation of GR is crucial for sustainable groundwater use, particularly in shallow aquifer regions that are sensitive to anthropogenic and climate change responses (Döll, 2009; Healy, 2010; Gong et al., 2023). There are several methods for recharge estimation (Allison, 1988; Foster, 1988). The water level fluctuation (WLF) method is a hydrological technique used to estimate groundwater recharge by monitoring changes in the water level of a well over time. The method has been used to estimate groundwater recharge in the present study. The method is considered to be one of the most promising techniques for shallow aquifers that display sharp water-level rises and declines in response to precipitation (Xu et al., 2024). Tidal corrections are applied to the WLF approach for the atoll. Wetting fronts during recharge do not disperse over short distances of thin unsaturated layers, and they show a sharp response. Typical shallow atoll aquifers are the most suitable example for the WLF method.

The outflow of the model includes evapotranspiration, subsurface groundwater discharge (SGD), and groundwater draft may cause a serious water scarcity problem shortly due to over-extraction, including seawater intrusion, land subsidence, and environmental damage (Gau and Liu, 2002).

Figure 1. Conceptual drawing of the shallow atoll aquifer system of Lakshadweep Archipelago. The groundwater inputs are: precipitation, and the outputs are: evapotranspiration, subsurface groundwater discharge (SGD), and groundwater discharge

Various numerical models can predict groundwater flow and contaminant transport, such as SUTRA, SEAWAT, FEFLOW, and MODFLOW (Sappa and Coviello, 2012). SEAWAT (a three-dimensional variable-density groundwater flow and transport mode) that couples Darcy's Law Interface and the Solute Transport Interface is a proven method to explore the behavior of the aquifer system. The variable density flow approach, which satisfies physical conditions more realistically by allowing a transition zone between freshwater and saltwater, is helpful in answering the gradual salinity increase by changing the model inputs (Park, 2004). In the paper, the numerical model is successfully used to validate the mathematical water budget model. This paper aims to assess saltwater intrusion in the coastal aquifers under varying groundwater abstraction conditions of one of the atolls of the Lakshadweep archipelago to develop a precise groundwater balance model of the aquifer for evaluation of safe yield.

Accurate measurement of optimal pumping rate is critical because negative aquifer balance

SITE DESCRIPTIONS

The Lakshadweep group has twenty-seven islands, several sunken banks, open reefs, and sandbanks spreading over an area of 32 sq. km between 8° N-12°30' N and 71° E-74° E in the Arabian Sea. It has ten inhabited and 17 uninhabited islands. Androth is one of the atolls of the archipelago that is located at 10°48'33"N and 73°40'E. The area of the island

is 4.8 sq. km. It is the easternmost, largest, and most highly populated atoll of the Lakshadweep group (Figure 2).

The island features a surface layer of approximately 1-2 meters of coral debris, followed by a compact yet porous crust of limestone conglomerate. Encircling the lagoons of Lakshadweep Island are coral reefs, which are linked to the open sea via various openings (Chakraborty and Ramesh, 1997). Recorded temperatures exhibit seasonal variations from 27.5°C to 31.6°C (Suresh and Mathew, 1993). The primary factor driving seasonal variability is the changes in sea surface temperature (SST) resulting from upwelling during the southwest monsoon (Chakraborty and Ramesh, 1997).

The annual average rainfall of the atoll is 1600 mm. About 72% of the annual rainfall is received during the southwest monsoon during the months of June to September and 28% during the northeast monsoon from October to December. The atoll aquifers are generally small and fragile systems that occur as thin lenses floating over saline water. Kumar, et al. (1986) carried out a brief topographical study of the archipelago (Figure 3). Adiga (1989) documented the sedimentary characteristics and geomorphic configuration of the Islands. Pathak and Kotnala (1990) predicted a rise in sea level, and Chandramohan et al. (1993) studied shoreline dynamics for the island group. Mannadiar (1977) and Tripathi (1999) have described the geological settings of the archipelago. The atoll is located in the tropics and experiences a warm and humid climate.

Figure 2. Geographical location of the Lakshadweep archipelago and the map of the study area, Androth. Points are the bore well locations for the water table measurements in the atoll

METHODOLOGY

The groundwater-balance method is the most widely used method for estimating safe yield for shallow aquifers. Daily time series records of precipitation, sea tides, and water level data are collected using rain gauges and water loggers installed in dug wells and seas. Groundwater draft, radiation hours, and temperature data are collected from regional government organizations. To compute the yearly average water balance of the atoll, it is necessary to individually estimate all the components of the model (e.g. total inflow and outflows of the aquifer). In ideal conditions, the inflows must balance with the outflows in addition to any change in storage, viz,

$$\sum \text{Input} = \sum \text{Output} \pm \Delta S$$

Here ΔS is a change in groundwater storage. The change in groundwater storage (ΔS) has been estimated by taking the difference between the average water level at the beginning and the end of the hydrological year. Validation of the model is done by a variable density numerical model that is developed based on hydrogeological and hydrological parameters of the aquifer used for the groundwater balance model.

A wide range of data, based on detailed geological and hydrogeological investigations, has been collected from the study site for accurate estimation of all the water flux components of the model. Evapotranspiration is measured using the Thornthwaite and SGD investigative methods, including direct measurement via hydrological estimation using Darcy's law. The water level fluctuation (WLF) method is adopted to estimate the natural recharge of the atoll. The groundwater draft data has been collected from the regional government office of the atoll.

Computation of the water balance components

Input

Recharge through precipitation

Precipitation serves as the sole source of recharge to the small atoll, underscoring the importance of accurately measuring precipitation and computing recharge (De Vries and Simmers, 2002; Jie et al., 2011). Daily precipitation levels are gauged using precipitation gauges strategically positioned across the atoll. Groundwater recharge constitutes a critical variable, and the precise quantification of groundwater recharge is vital for the sustainable management of groundwater resources (Gehrels et al., 2001). It stands as a crucial parameter essential for groundwater budgeting. (Louie et al., 2000; Otto, 2001; Yeh

et al., 2004). However, estimating recharge has proven to be a formidable challenge (Sharda et al., 2006). Here, the Richards equation is employed to characterize the water dynamics within the unsaturated zone of the soil profile.

$$\delta\theta/\delta t = \delta/\delta t [S(h)\delta h/\delta Z + S(h)] - W$$

Where θ is the soil volumetric water content; S is the saturation infiltration coefficient (cm/day); h is the hydraulic head (cm); W is the source-sink term (cm³/day) and t is time (in day).

To estimate groundwater recharge, hydrogeologists have employed physical, chemical, and/or numerical methods (Sophocleous, 1991). Numerous techniques exist for quantifying groundwater recharge, each with its own set of advantages and limitations (Beekman and Xu, 2003). Many researchers (Philip, 1957; Parlange, 1971; Morel-Seytoux, 1978; Smith and Parlange, 1978) have developed mathematical models to estimate groundwater recharge through unsaturated zones.

In the present study, the hydraulic head fluctuations (WTFs) technique, is used for estimating groundwater recharge (Healy and Cook, 2002). The water-table fluctuations (WTFs) method, using time series water level records from wells, is applied as early as the 1920s (Meinzer, 1923; Meinzer and Stearns, 1929; Sophocleous, 1991).

This method provides an estimate of groundwater recharge by monitoring changes in the hydraulic head due to the pressure exerted by groundwater in shallow observation wells by installing loggers to accurately measure groundwater levels to measure groundwater levels accurately. Tidal correction is applied to calculate the average daily water level of six existing wells to identify the water level rise that is attributable to precipitation (Todd, 1980). The yearly fluctuations in the water table, correlated with rainfall, are depicted in Figure 4. The method assumes that an increase in hydraulic head elevation, as observed in shallow wells, is attributed to the influx of recharge across the hydraulic head. Recharge is estimated as (Avery et al., 1999; Ketchum et al., 2000):

$$R(t) = S_y \times \Delta H(t)$$

Where $R(t)$ is recharge at time t , S_y is specific yield, and $\Delta H(t)$ is the peak water level rise at time t , attributed to the recharge period. According to Boumis et al. (2022), all recharge received by the groundwater is presumed to translate into an elevation in the groundwater level, with the change in groundwater level being calculated as the

difference between the current day's level and the previous day's level., i.e., $\Delta H = H_i - H_{i-1}$.

Figure 3. A flow diagram showing the methodology to calculate the atoll groundwater balance where rainfall is the only source of groundwater recharge as an input. Evapotranspiration (ET) where water lost are through canopy interception and evaporation, Subsurface Groundwater Discharge (SGD) where water losses are through direct subsurface drainage to ocean, and direct groundwater discharge (Q) are three dominant outputs from the atoll aquifer. Note that S_y is specific yield, and $\Delta H(t)$ is the peak water level rise at time t , attributed to the recharge period in the groundwater balance model.

Hydraulic head rise is determined by computing the variance between the peaks of the water level rise and the minimum water level value obtained from the recession curve using a water level logger (Banerjee and Singh, 2011). Extrapolating the recession curve is not always straightforward due to influences from various recharge factors (Banerjee et al., 2008). However, precipitation-driven recharge predominantly governs the average water level in shallow aquifer systems like atoll aquifers. The aquifer's specific yield (S_y) is regarded as a storage term, determined through field approaches such as aquifer testing methods. Pumping tests and tidal response analyses are employed to estimate the hydrogeological parameters of the study area (Banerjee et al., 2011, 2012).

Outputs

Peterson (1984) elucidated that on most small atolls, the permeability of surface materials is sufficiently high to render surface runoff negligible, thus excluding it from water budget calculations. Consequently, the primary output components in the area consist of evapotranspiration, subsurface groundwater discharge (SGD), and abstraction. Notably, there is no agricultural activity within the atoll.

Evapotranspiration

Evapotranspiration (ET) is a crucial process in the hydrological cycle where water is transferred from the Earth's surface to the atmosphere in the form of water vapor, where it comprises evaporation and transpiration (Groeneveld et al., 2007; Yeh et al., 2007). Several formulae exist for calculating evapotranspiration, each tailored to specific conditions and data availability, such as Penman-Monteith Equation (Xing et al., 2023), Thornthwaite Equation (Smith, 1965), Hargreaves-Samani

Equation (Wootton et al., 2020), Pan Evaporation Method (Kisi, 2015) and Crop Coefficient Method (Guo et al., 2020), etc. In tropical atolls, daylight plays a crucial role, influencing various aspects of the environment. Therefore, in this study, the Thornthwaite method is employed. This method is recognized as one of the most reliable and optimized approaches for water-budget estimation, particularly in tropical regions (Thornthwaite and Mather, 1957). The formula is mainly based on temperature with an adjustment being made for the number of daylight hours. The method offers an effective solution to the evaporimeter problem due to its freedom from assumptions, minimal reliance on arbitrary constants, reduced potential for measurement errors, and suitability for tropical environments (Pelton et al., 1960).

formula derives potential evaporation, based on mean air temperature and day length, the two significant factors that exert dominant influence in the region. Thornthwaite's (Thornthwaite and Mather, 1955) formula for computing monthly potential evapotranspiration is given as,

$$E_p = 1.6(10T/D)^a$$

Thornthwaite approach in a monthly time scale improved if an "effective" temperature (T_{ef}) is used instead of the average temperature [$T_{avg} = 0.5(T_{max} + T_{min})$]. The effective temperature was computed empirically as a function of the average temperature and of the daily amplitude ($A = T_{max} - T_{min}$) as,

$$T_{ef} = k(T_{avg} + A) = 1/2 k(3T_{max} - T_{min}) \text{ or } T_{ef} = .36(3T_{max} - T_{min})$$

with $k = 0.72$ as the statistically best value for estimating ETM (Pereira and Pruitt, 2004).

Figure 4. Mean monthly water level after tidal correction and precipitation recorded at Androth Island, Lakshwadeep (India)

The Thornthwaite approach for estimating potential evaporation has gained broader acceptance and has been used to estimate groundwater balance in tropical coastal aquifers (Voddouris, 2006). It is well-suited for tropical climatic conditions, as the

$$E_p = 1.6(10T_{ef}/I)^a$$

Where E_p is monthly potential evapotranspiration (cm); E'_p is corrected potential evapotranspiration (mm); T = mean monthly temperature ($^{\circ}C$); T_{ef} = effective monthly temperature ($^{\circ}C$); I = heat index for a given area, which is the sum of 12 monthly index values i . Here, i is derived from mean monthly temperatures using the following formula:

$$i = (T/5)^{1.514}$$

'i' is the monthly heat index, where T is the mean temperature of the month under consideration is expressed in degree Celsius. Twelve monthly indices are added to give an annual heat index I. a is an empirically derived exponent which is a function of I,

$$a = 6.75 \times 10^{-7} I^3 - 7.71 \times 10^{-5} I^2 + 1.79 \times 10^{-2} I$$

An estimate of the potential evapotranspiration is calculated every month in 'mm.' Multiplying the E_p value by one factor N, which depends on latitude, gives the corrected potential evapotranspiration (E'_p). N is the monthly adjustment factor related to hours of daylight. This formula is based mainly on temperature with an adjustment being made for the number of daylight hours. The monthly mean temperatures have been taken from the measurements at a local climatological station for estimation of the potential evaporation for each month of the year.

When $E'_p \leq P$ then $E_r = E'_p$

In this case, water surplus is given by

$$S_i = P - E_r \text{ and } W_{S_i} = W_{\max}$$

where P is the rainfall, the average monthly rainfall for ten years is used in the study. S_i is the total water surplus (infiltration and runoff), W_{S_i} is the water amount in the soil for I month, and W_{\max} is the maximum water storage in the soil (constant) depending on the soil features. Coral islands are composed of coral sands. These coral sands are white colored and fine textured sand. The W_{\max} of these fine sands is about 90 mm water/ m soil.

When $E'_p \geq P$ then $E_r = P + |\Delta W_S|$, and where P is rainfall (mm) and E_r is real evapotranspiration.

$$\Delta W_S = W_{S_i} - W_{S_{i-1}}$$

The water amount in the soil (W_{S_i}) for i month is calculated as

$$W_{S_i} = W_{\max} e^{-(APWL/W_{\max})}$$

where W_{\max} is the maximum water storage in the soil; APWL is the accumulated potential water loss $(P - E'_p)$.

In this case water surplus $S_i = 0$. It is pointed out that a water surplus exists if the water storage in the soil has the maximum value.

Submarine groundwater discharge (SGD)

Despite the high rate of percolation through the highly permeable coral sands, the net recharge remains meager due to a significant portion of the recharge flowing out to the sea as submarine groundwater discharge (SGD). The significance of SGD as a source of subsurface groundwater flux to the sea has garnered increasing recognition and constitutes a significant aspect of groundwater balance studies. Previous studies have primarily focused on methods to quantify SGD, either through point measurements (Bokuniewicz, 1980; Moore, 1996; Bugna et al., 1996; Kim et al., 2003; Michael et al., 2003), hydro-geologic models (Smith and Zawadzki, 2003; Destouni and Prieto, 2003), or by using geochemical tracers that provide a spatially integrated estimate of total flux (Moore and Arnold, 1996). In the current study, hydrological assessments of fresh submarine groundwater discharge (SGD) were derived from data collected from groundwater monitoring wells situated along the coastline. These pre-existing wells boast substantial diameters and average a depth of approximately 7.5 meters. Throughout the investigation, water levels were monitored employing both an electronic water level meter and a pressure data logger.

Previous studies indicate that the tidal effect would provide a convenient, economical, and reliable way to identify coastal hydrogeological conditions and interactions on a large scale (Ferris, 1951; Carr and Kamp, 1969; Merritt, 2004). The tidal method and pumping test method are conducted at several wells to estimate the horizontal hydraulic conductivity of aquifer sediments (Banerjee et al., 2008, 2011). Standard pumping tests were performed, and water level response in each well was measured with electronic water level tape and with a pressure transducer installed prior to the test at an interval of 1 s.

Formulation of groundwater simulation model

The model was developed using Visual MODFLOW and employed the SEAWAT solver at different stages: initial model setup, discharge, layer creation, assigning permeability (K), importing observation well data for head (Saleh, 2007), concentration, and defining boundary conditions. This is a variable density finite difference numerical model developed by the US Geological Survey (Langevin and Guo, 1999). Upon completion of model creation, it underwent calibration through the SEAWAT engine as needed. The simulation was configured to run and simulate the present and future groundwater balance for the study area. The following steps are followed:

- (i) The model domain was created using a map covering the study area with a node spacing of 2 m.
- (ii) Head values of the observation wells were used for simulation and the models were appropriate for simulation of groundwater flow balance using the data applied in the groundwater balance model.
- (ii) The hydrogeological and transport parameters were assigned for measured conductivity (m/day), discharge (m³/s), recharge (mm/yr), diffusion coefficient (m²/day), and longitudinal dispersity (m).
- (iv) Chloride concentration was chosen as the primary chemical indicator of saltwater intrusion and the simulation period is one year. Forecasting of the aquifer responses was simulated considering the present aquifer conditions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Input

Rainfall recharge (Q_r)

Recharge is delineated as the inflow of water into the saturated zone (Freeze and Cherry, 1979; Healy and Cook, 2002; DeVries and Simmers, 2002; Yeh et al., 2007). The water level fluctuation method is a conventional recharge estimation technique used for the recharge estimation of the

study area characterized by the shallow aquifer. Time series rainfall data and water level data observed from six existing wells in the study area have been measured, as shown in Figure 3. The island aquifer is shallow, and the hydraulic head displays sharp water-level rises and declines with infiltrated water percolating rapidly in the coral sand aquifer. Recharge is prominent during the summer rainy seasons, between June and September when the monsoon brings intensive precipitation events. The soil profile has approximately uniform hydrological properties and infiltrated water is instantaneously and uniformly distributed. Also, the area is approximately uniform in terms of elevation, geology, land surface, and vegetation. The calculated average recharge value is $3.0 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

Output

Evapotranspiration (ET)

In tropical regions, the evapotranspiration rate is high compared to other regions. Real evapotranspiration of the Androth Island (E_r) is 200.066 mm/yr (Figure 5). Estimation of the water balance by using the Thornthwaite method is calculated as shown in Table 1. Thus the total output is $3.17 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$.

Table 1. Monthly potential evapotranspiration calculated using Thornthwaite formula, where T is monthly average temperature (°C), I is monthly thermal index, E_r is Real evapotranspiration, E_p is potential evapotranspiration, APWL is the accumulated potential water loss, W_s is water amount in the soil, N is the monthly adjustment factor related to hours of daylight, E'p is corrected potential evapotranspiration and Sr is water surplus.

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Temp(°C)	27.4	28.1	28.9	29.2	29.9	28	27.3	27.4	27.7	27.9	27.8	27.4
I	13.1	13.6	14.2	15	14.9	13.5	13	13.1	13.5	13.5	13.4	13.1
Ep (mm)	14.7	16.4	18.6	21.6	21.4	16.1	14.4	14.4	15.4	15.9	15.6	14.8
N	1	0.9	1.03	1.03	1.08	1.06	1	1	1	1	0.9	0.9
E'p (mm)	147	149.2	192.2	222.8	231.9	171.2	156.3	156.3	157.2	162.2	153.4	146.7
P (mm)	11.4	28.5	0	55.5	185.4	413.2	251.5	251.5	169.2	259.2	124.8	24
P-E'p	-135.6	-120.7	-192.2	-167.3	-46.4	242	95.2	276.6	12	97.3	-28.6	-122.7
APWL	-135.6	-157.2	-349.4	-516.7	-563.2	0	0	0	0	0	-591.8	-714.5
Ws(mm)	19.9	15.68	1.85	0.29	0.17	90	90	90	90	90	0.13	0.03
ΔWs (mm)	19.9	-4.2	-13.8	-1.56	-0.12	89	0	0	0	0	-89.87	0.1
Er (mm)	31.3	32.8	13.8	57	185.5	171.2	156.3	158.5	157.2	162.2	214.6	24.1
Sr (mm)	0	0	0	0	0	242	95.2	276.6	12	97.3	0	0

Figure 5. Average monthly precipitation (P), the potential evapotranspiration (E_p) and real evapotranspiration (E_r) in the Androth Island

Subsurface outflows (Q_3)

Depth of the water in the wells of peripheral parts of the aquifers ranges from 5 m to 2 m down to sea-level along the coast. Hydrologic estimates of fresh SGD are obtained using data from groundwater monitoring wells placed along the coast and calculated hydraulic gradient varies from 0.001 near the top of the lens to 0.006 toward the coast. Data from the pumping test and tidal method reveals hydraulic transmissivity values ranging from 45-300 $m^2 day^{-1}$ (Figure 5). These values fall within the expected range for permeable sands (Freeze and Cherry, 1979). Groundwater flow rates calculated using Darcy’s law, hydraulic gradient data, and the geometric mean of measured hydraulic conductivity reveal near shore horizontal groundwater velocities. The calculated result of average SGD and water loss in coral sand is approximately 25% of the total recharge and is $0.75 \times 10^6 m^3 yr^{-1}$.

Domestic water uses (Q_2)

Based on the records of the regional government office’s report, the annual average domestic draft for the island is $2.4 \times 10^6 m^3 yr^{-1}$.

Groundwater balance

Storage change is often estimated as the residual of outflow and inflow, both of which are estimated with variable uncertainty (Camp et. al., 2010). The estimated water

balance shows that the groundwater abstraction from the island aquifer system exceeds the recharge. Thus, it is obvious that the aquifer system is overexploited. Groundwater overexploitation, being practiced by abstraction from over 40 wells and boreholes, that has resulted in significant head decline and seawater intrusion.

Groundwater balance = Total water input – total water output = $-0.17 \times 10^6 m^3 yr^{-1}$.

Estimation of safe yield

The study applied a novel technique to estimate the safe yield for fragile atoll aquifers. The main water input and outputs are measured to calculate the water budget in order to assess the safe yield of the aquifer. Safe yield (Naik and Awasthi, 2003) is computed and used as a viable management concept:

$$\text{Safe yield for island aquifer} = Q_{ed} + Q_{dom}$$

Where Q_{ed} (the exploitable dynamic groundwater reserve) is reserve exploitable dynamic groundwater and Q_{dom} is the volume of water used for domestic use in the rainy season. Q_{ed} is calculated by the formula:

$$Q_{ed} = A \times S_y \times DI_d$$

Where, S_y is the specific yield, A is the effective area for groundwater recharge and DI_d is the average water level

decline in the dry period (December to April). The exploitable dynamic groundwater represents the long-term average annual recharge under condition of maximum groundwater use.

Estimation of Specific yield

Based on the water-level rise and wet-season recharge for the year, we can estimate the specific yield using the following equation (Goes, 1999):

$$R = S_y \times A \times Dl_w + Q_{ab} + Q_{sd}$$

where R is the recharge in wet season, S_y is the specific yield, A is the effective area for groundwater recharge, Dl_w is the average water level rise in the wet period (May to November), Q_{ad} is the groundwater abstraction during the recharge period, that is equal to the volume of water used for domestic use in the rainy season, and is the lateral subsurface discharge. The average water level rise in the wet period (May to November) is 1-2 m. Domestic abstraction for the rainy season is about $1.7 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ and subsurface groundwater discharge from the aquifer is $0.8 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$. The accepted average level rise value is 1.6 m, and groundwater recharge during the monsoon is $3.22 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$. Thus the specific yield is estimated to be 0.161 Or 16.1%. By substituting the specific yield, the effective area and average water level decline found during the dry period is 1.5-2.5 m, and the exploitable dynamic is calculated as $1.8 \times$

$10^6 \text{ m}^3\text{yr}^{-1}$. Thus the safe yield is calculated as 2.7×10^6 to $3.06 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3\text{yr}^{-1}$.

Formulation of groundwater simulation model using SEAWAT

The calibration of the model involves aligning simulated piezometric head levels with corresponding observed values throughout the study area. A sensitivity analysis was performed concerning hydraulic conductivity, storage coefficients, and head, where values were taken from Banerjee et al. (2008). The groundwater flow model is performed to identify the behavior of the water level that is calculated for the next 6 months, 1.5 years, 3 years, and five years respectively, using the annual average recharge as the input flux. Hydraulic heads and permeability of the aquifer are considered calibration parameters (Figure 6). Higher-density saline water is established in the boundary of the aquifer. Initial and boundary conditions are kept similar for all the simulations.

The simulation solution strategy is proposed to solve the subsurface flow system of the atoll and simulation results are given in Table 2. The intrusion processes are examined under annual average recharge and actual abstraction conditions. The findings, as depicted in Figure 7, indicate a gradual migration of the transition zone towards land over time. This suggests a significant influence of groundwater withdrawal on the seawater intrusion process.

Figure 6. Map showing the hydraulic transmissivity distribution (after Banerjee and Singh, 2011). Lat. and Long. on vertical and horizontal axis are in degree

Table 2. Model simulation error and run period information

(a)	Model validation	Values
	Normalize RMS	3.50%
	Correlation coefficient	0.99
	Absolute mean error	0.008 (m)
(b)	Simulation with different time	Time
	Scenario A	6 Months
	Scenario B	1.5 Years
	Scenario C	3 Years
	Scenario D	5 Years

Figure 7. Simulation results of numerical models for varying groundwater abstraction periods (a) 180 days, (b) 360 days, (c) 1096 days and (d) 1826 days. Dotted points are dug well locations

Interestingly, the results align with the mathematical model of groundwater balance outcomes. This suggests that the groundwater balance model exhibits strong predictive capability regarding the water balance status of the atoll aquifer system.

CONCLUSIONS

Atolls of Lakshadweep archipelago are highly vulnerable to climate change impacts such as sea-level rise, increased storm surges, and changes in rainfall patterns. Also, it is necessary to determine the island's water requirements and the sources of water supply. Implementing water conservation and efficiency measures is critical for sustainable groundwater management. Groundwater sustainable management planning in the atoll island of Lakshadweep requires a multifaceted approach that addresses hydrogeological constraints, water demand, conservation measures, climate change adaptation, governance, and community involvement. Atolls typically have limited land area, low elevation, and are composed of porous coral sand, which affects the recharge and movement of groundwater, therefore comprehensive understanding of the hydrogeological conditions is crucial that should include groundwater management plans, which should incorporate climate change adaptation strategies. The present study of the assessment of groundwater balance modeling for optimum yield estimation in atolls provided critical insights into the sustainability and management of these fragile ecosystems.

- (i) The estimation of groundwater balance and determination of safe yield were crucial measures for ensuring the sustainability of the atoll aquifers and mitigating environmental degradation, particularly concerning seawater intrusion.
- (ii) The findings underscore the importance of accurately estimating safe withdrawal rates and formulating robust policies based on comprehensive groundwater monitoring and aquifer understanding.
- (iii) The study underscores that seawater intrusion and aquifer depletion are exacerbated by rising groundwater extraction rates, this research underscores the urgent need for proactive measures to safeguard these vital water resources.
- (iv) Integrated management strategies, supported by interdisciplinary collaborations and community engagement, offer a holistic approach to address the complex challenges facing atoll ecosystems.

- (v) Collective action and shared responsibility are essential, underscoring the interconnectedness of scientific inquiry, policy formulation, and community engagement in achieving sustainable water management.
- (vi) Ultimately, our journey through groundwater balance modeling in atolls highlights the power of knowledge, collaboration, and collective action in shaping a more sustainable future for our planet's vulnerable aquatic environments.
- (vii) Future research endeavors hold promise for refining groundwater models to gain new insights into aquifer dynamics and exploring alternative water resources to enhance resilience in the face of scarcity and uncertainty.

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Author credit statement

Dr. Pallavi Banerjee Chattopadhyay conceptualized the idea and guided the two project interns, Debadatta Chatterjee and Satwik Bhattacharya, to perform numerical modeling and computational analysis, writing and editing the whole manuscript. Dr. V.S. Singh and Dr. Pallavi Banerjee Chattopadhyay contributed to the fieldwork and data collection.

Data Availability

The monthly rainfall and temperature data for Lakshadweep, India were sourced from Indian Meteorological Department Thiruvananthapuram, India. The population and average groundwater abstraction data were sourced from the Ground Water Department, Government of Kerala, India. Hydraulic conductivity and storage coefficient data were obtained through pumping

tests conducted at the site, and the information extracted from Banerjee and Singh et al. (2011).

Compliance with ethical standards

We declare that there are no competing interests related to any financial concern about the publication of this study. It is being declared that there are no personal relationships with people or organizations that may influence or may be perceived to influence the research work described in this paper. We adhere to copyright norms.

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